

N3C Tenant Pilot Report

October 5, 2023

Pilot Leadership

Melissa Haendel

University of Colorado Anschutz

Chris Chute

John Hopkins University

Emily Pfaff

University of North Carolina -Chapel Hill

Richard Moffitt

Emory University

Anita Walden

University of Colorado Anschutz

Christine Suver

Sage Biotechnology

Johanna Loomba

University of Virginia

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Overview

The National COVID Cohort Collaborative (N3C) has seen tremendous success and impact from its COVID-focused Enclave, housing the largest national, and publicly available patient-level limited dataset. N3C is expanding beyond COVID to launch a pilot project to evaluate the feasibility of conducting non-covid research using the existing secure Enclave infrastructure. The pilot project expanded to three non-COVID conditions; Alzheimer's Disease and Related Dementias, Renal, and Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease. The purpose of this pilot project was to establish efficient, scalable governance and data contribution processes supporting multiple research enclaves, and to provide researchers with agency and a secure computing platform to conduct analyses to address local and national questions. Twelve sites participated in a pilot of three clinical tenant projects and access was provided to Level 2 de-identified data.

This document describes the process for creating the data infrastructure, project governance, and the project teams. Information about what worked well and what should be done differently is also documented in this report, along with a proposed future vision for the tenants.

Pilot Completion

The Tenant Pilot project was successfully completed. Successful completion of the pilot was defined when at least two sites were able to contribute data to at least one tenant, analyses were performed to produce counts of patients and visits meeting a disease specific phenotype. All three pilot clinical projects achieved this milestone. All 10 data-contributing sites completed the IRB processes, 9 of the 10 successfully submitted data, and 11 sites successfully participated in the clinical projects. One site decided not to participate because neither of the tenants included questions related to children.

Resources/Links

- [Tenant One-Pager \(Long\)](#)

Pilot Sites and Project Selection

The following sites were participants in the tenant pilot project. They were selected based on their past involvement in the N3C effort and their desire to expand the infrastructure for non-COVID research. Ten sites were selected as data contributing sites and 2 sites were voted to participate as analytics only participants.

The following organizations participated in at least one of the 3 tenants. The organizations in bold have contributed data.

- **John Hopkins University**
- **University of Nebraska**
- **Oregon Health & Science University**
- **University of North Carolina Health Care System**
- **OCHIN Inc**

- **University of Chicago**
- **University of Washington**
- **University of Virginia (UVA)**
- **University of Colorado School of Medicine**
 - **Colorado Children’s Hospital**
- ***Stanford University - did not submit data***
- Emory University
- Stony Brook University

An open call was made to the community (via weekly governance calls) to generate a list of pilot clinical topics. Clinical champions were recruited for each topic, who were tasked with defining a research question for each potential pilot project ([link to project descriptions](#)). Data contributing sites were then given the opportunity to vote for the projects to be included in the pilot. Results of each site’s preferences were compiled and provided to NCATS, who ultimately decided which clinical tenants would be part of the pilot. One site decided to pause their participation in the pilot, because the selected projects were not relevant to children.

Governance

Approach

Building on the success and infrastructure of the N3C we expanded team science beyond the pandemic response. We leveraged the successful collaborative approach and governance knowledge acquired in N3C to develop the governance for the Tenant Model Pilot that greatly increases agency over the use of and access to the data by the data-contributing organizations.

Three projects were piloted the tenant model:

- Alzheimer’s Disease and Related Dementias: An exploration of relationships between comorbidities and dementia sub-phenotypes
- Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease: An evaluation of outcomes in COPD sub-populations after short vs long steroid course prescribed at the time of acute exacerbations
- Renal Disease: An investigation of disparities in the coding of kidney injury.

The Governance working group, composed of the N3C leadership, NCATS and pilot participating organizations, collaboratively developed the rules that govern participation in a Tenant. A Code of Conduct, Community Guiding Principles, and Attribution and Publication Principles were developed for the N3C Tenant Model Pilot.

The [N3C Tenant Pilot User Code of Conduct](#) articulates fundamental actions and prohibitions on data user activities involving data or other resources accessible through the N3C Tenant Pilot Data Enclave and reflects the data use terms and conditions outlined in the **Participation Agreement** entered into by participating institutions and NCATS.

This [N3C Tenant Pilot Community Guiding Principles](#) outlines expectations of every N3C Tenant Pilot Data Enclave community member which includes institutions and individuals who use the N3C Tenant

Pilot Data Enclave resources, expertise, and data. The N3C Tenant Pilot is built on the principles of Partnership, Inclusivity, Transparency, Reciprocity, Accountability, Security, and Mutual Respect:

- **Partnership:** N3C Tenant Pilot community members are trusted partners committed to honoring the N3C Tenant Pilot Community Guiding Principles and Code of Conduct
- **Inclusivity:** The N3C Tenant Pilot is open to investigators invited by data-contributing organizations to use the N3C Tenant Pilot data to conduct collaborative research and contribute insights
- **Transparency:** Descriptions of projects are posted publicly.
- **Reciprocity:** Contributions are acknowledged, and results from analyses, including provenance and attribution, are expected to be shared with the researcher community.
- **Accountability:** The N3C Tenant Pilot community members take responsibility for their activities and hold each other accountable for achieving the research ' objectives and acting through good scientific practices.
- **Security:** All activities are conducted in a secure, controlled access cloud-based environment. Data and workflows are recorded for auditing and attribution purposes. The recordings are accessible to N3C Tenant Pilot leadership.
- **Mutual respect:** Communications should be professional, concise, clear and relevant. Follow proper communication etiquette articulated below. Avoid excessive conflict, unprofessional arguments, ad hominem attacks, and/or ridicule over chat and in messaging.

The revised [N3C Attribution and Publication Principles](#) provides community-driven guidelines and approaches that all users within the N3C research community uphold, and it addresses attribution and publication principles regarding N3C Community dissemination of research on COVID-19 and on the three N3C Tenant Pilot projects.

IRB

The Johns Hopkins (JHU) IRB approved the initial application on September 29, 2022, including approval of JHU as a site. The reliance process was initiated with IRB reliance sites in January 2023, with the JHU IRB reviewing and approving individual reliance sites during the March to July 2023 time period. To date, 11 reliance sites have been approved by the JHU IRB. The list below notes the IRB approval date for each site.

- Johns Hopkins University (approved 9/29/2022)
- University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill (approved 3/7/2023)
- University of Virginia (approved 3/7/2023)
- OCHIN (approved 3/29/2023)
- Oregon Health & Science University (approved 4/5/2023)
- Stanford University (approved 4/19/2023)
- University of Colorado Denver (approved 4/19/2023)
- University of Nebraska Medical Center (approved 5/8/2023)

- University of Chicago (approved 5/10/2023)
- University of Washington (approved 6/7/2023)
- Children’s Hospital Colorado (approved 07/26/2023)
- UCHealth (approved 7/27/2023)

Decisions Made by Group

Voting Approach

The governance working group decided that the project tenants were open by default, allowing each organization contributing data to join any of the 3 project tenants. Each data-contributing organization had one voting member in each tenant. Voting members decided whether to invite researchers from non data-contributing sites and votes were required to be unanimous.

Data and Non-Data Contributors

Sites elected to participate by providing data or expertise as Clinicians, Analysts, Statisticians, Subject Matter Experts (SME) or Project Managers. The table below summarizes the level of participation by each site in each of the three tenant projects.

Tenant Model Level of Participation			
Site Name	Alzheimer's	Pulmonary	Renal Disease
Emory	Not Participating	Not Participating	analysis only
John Hopkins University	data and analysis	data and analysis	data and analysis
OCHIN	data only	data and analysis	data and analysis
OHSU	data and analysis	Not Participating	data and analysis
Stanford	Not Participating	Not Participating	Not Participating
University of Chicago	data and analysis	data and analysis	data and analysis
University of Colorado Anschutz	data and analysis	data and analysis	data and analysis
Children's Hospital Colorado	TBD	TBD	TBD
University of Nebraska Medical Center	data and analysis	data and analysis	data and analysis
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill	data and analysis	data only	data and analysis
University of Virginia	data and analysis	data and analysis	data and analysis
University of Washington	data and analysis	data only	data and analysis
Stony Brook	Not Participating	Not Participating	analysis only

DUR Decision Map for Non-data Contributors

Data Integration and Harmonization Approach

Approach

For this pilot generalization effort, we created a longitudinal patient phenotype as a prototype. The longitudinal requirements were rudimentary, but reflect the fact that since analyses of real-world data implies some kind of condition or intervention followed by some kind of outcome, only patients at sites that have repeated visits are very informative. Patients that have only a single visit, or even simply two widely spaced visits, offer less continuity or epidemiologic value.

Furthermore, we recognized that from a single master data submission, multiple sub-cohorts could be created for tenant specific enclaves.

Tenant Workflow

This is the workflow process for the pilot tenant process from data submission to analytic report

Data Acquisition Process

The process was modeled after N3C COVID which was already familiar to sites. The data submission scripts were greatly simplified for local extracts given there was no need for building matched cohorts or running any tenant specific scripts. Additional phenotyping was done for all sites within the operational workspace prior to releasing subsets of the data to the secure tenant workspaces.

Data Acquisition Phenotype

Inclusion criteria:

- Patients of all ages
- Having a duration of record of at least 2 years since 2018
- Having at least
 - 3 blood pressure measurements on different dates
 - OR
 - 3 charted diagnoses codes on different dates

Data Elements transmitted:

- Demographics, including zip code
- A hashed identifier to support future linkage with imaging, death data, or other major national data resources with a shared hash identifier (below).
- Encounters/Visits and related information, including dates
- Laboratory tests and results, including dates
- Medications, including start and where available stop dates
- Vital signs, with dates
- Diagnoses, with dates

- Procedures, with dates
- Admission, Discharge, Transfer information with dates
 - Including death with dates
- Extracted “observations” from ancillary sources such as notes
- The information was requested retrospectively to 1 Jan 2018 and through the present with
- periodic, serial data updates for a given patient.

Data Ingestion and Harmonization Data Flow

Each pilot site submitted data in one of two formats: OMOP or PCORnet. Sites were instructed to submit into the same incoming SFTP folder used for N3C. Each site’s zip file had the traditional N3C harmonization pipeline to map the data into OMOP. Traditional N3C data validation checks (such as ensuring unique IDs and the non-emptiness of required domains) were applied. Site data was then unioned and unit harmonized, in a pipeline similar to the N3C pipeline. For the tenant pilot, data was only in Level 2, so the date-shifting and desensitization steps were applied to the data.

The cleaned level 2 datasets then underwent the tenant extraction step:

1. Filtering down the data to sites who have opted in to a given tenant
2. Filtering down the data to the tenant phenotype.

Finally, data was released to researchers in the 3 tenant projects for analysis. An additional SDOH dataset was also released for each tenant, upon request from researchers.

Data Quality Pipeline

In order to quickly assess the quality of the data payloads after they are submitted and processed, a Data Quality Portal was constructed, supported by automated SQL and Python scripts, to provide a visual representation of current payload data quality. As Data Quality Portals had been previously constructed for N3C COVID and CMS datasets, setting up a new Data Quality Portal for the tenant datasets was quickly accomplished by reusing existing assets. The existing Data Quality Portal application was duplicated in the tenant workspace, and the reporting charts and tables contained within the application GUI were connected with the newly created tenant reporting metrics datasets. Finally, all Python and SQL scripts used to generate tenant reporting metrics datasets were added to an automated build schedule that would trigger when newly staged tenant data was available.

Some simple customizations were performed to configure the new Data Quality Portal for the tenant model datasets, including removal of COVID-specific metrics that are not of interest to the tenant models, and creation of new population counts by tenant model phenotype to report on patient populations by tenant model and data partner.

Data Access

Approved members were granted de-identified Level 2 access. Members for each site were required to submit a data use request for each tenant. Data-contributing sites identified a voting member for each tenant. The data-contributing sites were required to vote unanimously to allow non-data contributing sites to participate in a tenant.

Analytics

To ensure a successful project, each project required several participant roles on each team. The Clinical Champion and an Analytical Lead organized and led the project team. The project teams met on a regular basis and achieved the goals of the initial phase of the projects. Many of the roles were filled by volunteers during the pilot due to lack of funding.

Project Roles and Responsibilities

Role	Responsibilities
Project Champion (2 roles)	Ensure the mission is communicated; help define the clinical question; provide vision; participate in project calls. Owns/drives scientific questions. Stakeholders are engaged. Role 1 - clinical specific the domain Role 2- analytical (functional/content /data knowledge) - help assess quality of data and what should be included, direct analytical activities
Clinician	Provide clinical input on clinical questions and clinical phenotype. Create and review concept sets as needed
Analyst	Gathers, interprets, and uses complex data to develop actionable steps to improve performance and optimize results. Write code. Using the tools of statistics, analysts will help answer pressing research questions in medicine, biology and public health. Ensures experimental design is correct
Project Manager	Responsible for planning and execution of the project. Responsible for planning meetings, creating agendas, follow-up on action items, providing status updates, reporting to the group/community, identifying risks, removing obstacles, and moving the project forward.
Centralized group	
Data Liaison	Data liaisons help Clinicians create concept sets DL aligned to each project team, available during office hours (2 meetings a week)
Logic Liaison	Logic Liaison takes raw data and turns it into variables for analysis , providing all of their quality templates, combined variable templates. They will help all tenant teams (go to their recurring meetings/also available during office hours)

Tenant-specific phenotypes were constructed that were able to define the subset of patients relevant to each study. Only these relevant subsets of patients were provided to each tenant for further analysis.

<p>Alzheimer's Disease and Related Dementias</p>	<p>A team of clinicians, informaticians, and data scientists was assembled and began work on study design and concept set creation leading up to data availability. Data was sent by sites and a study phenotype was designed. Analysis of the data made available to tenant analysts confirmed that the study cohort matched the desired phenotype (see demographic report).</p> <p>The team has begun building a series of machine learning models that investigate the relationship between comorbidities and dementia subtypes. We are in the process of tuning models, evaluating sampling approaches, and refining feature sets, all of which will be described in a final manuscript.</p>
<p>COPD/ Pulmonary</p>	<p>A team of clinicians, informaticians, and data scientists was assembled and began work on study design and concept set creation leading up to data availability. Data was sent by sites and a study phenotype was designed. Analysis of the data made available to tenant analysts confirmed that the study cohort matched the desired phenotype (see demographic report).</p> <p>The team identified lack of days supply in the drug_occurrence data from the PCORnet sites (5 of the 8). This prohibited use of their data to answer the steroid use question. Although funding was not available to support enhanced data mappings at the site level, the team did recognize that these values might be salvaged from data that had been contributed but not mapped in the DI&H process. New mapping scripts were added. This resulted in obtaining the necessary data from 2 of the 5 PCORnet sites, allowing for adequate study power. Given this recent enhanced data availability, we are now finishing a series of logistic regressions and sensitivity analyses as planned. The improved DI&H mappings were then deployed across all tenants and N3C. This process highlighted the value of shared processes across multiple tenants.</p>
<p>Renal</p>	<p>Meeting notes for the renal tenant team are here. Data from 6 sites were available for use, and researchers from 7 institutions contributed to the project. We defined all of the instances of Acute Kidney Injury, predicated on establishing a baseline creatinine level for each patient. We then compared patient characteristics among those patients whose AKI was detected from serum creatinine alone (undiagnosed) versus those patients who had a documented diagnosis for AKI, and found that the undiagnosed group was younger and healthier. A preliminary report was approved for export and is available here.</p>

Pilot Metrics

To evaluate the project, it is important to provide the average amount of time for each step of the project. It took a total of 114 days from the approval of the IRB protocol to the last data submission to the pilot enclave.

Item	Date	Avg #days from NIH Participation Agreement sent to Execution
First Site IRB approved	3/7/23	0
NIH approved Participation Agreement Sent to sites	4/6/23	0
First Site to execute Participation Agreement	4/24/23	19 days
First site to submit data from NIH agreement Sent to site	5/11/23	36
First site to enter a tenant space	6/21/23	77
All 3 tenants have at least 2 sites with contributing data	6/21/23	77
Last Data submission	8/27/23	114

Feedback

Feedback was collected from the instructure team and the participating sites to learn what went well and what they think should be done differently in the future. Below is the feedback.

What Went Well

- Sites that participated in the pilot project were engaged in developing the governance framework. There was shared governance, robust attendance and authority.
- The open governance meetings and the initial champion plus clinical and analytical lead sign ups really helped to give the projects a structure and awareness that helped everything progress smoothly once we had all the data in.
- Platform staff (Palantir) responsiveness for this pilot was also excellent.
- People that hadn't worked on N3C previously asked to participate in the pilot.
- Slides that describe the data elements, data transfer process, the IRB and the location of the data helped with the internal site governance approval process.
- Was able to reuse or copy infrastructure from COVID to be used in the pilot. This includes copying the base code for the pipeline and the concept sets.
- Data quality measures
- Only one submission required by site
- Data Submission SFTP same as N3C
- SQL scripts and exporter workflow same as N3C

- Only one IRB protocol and one DUA/DTA were required of the sites for participation in the tenants
- Only one submission was required to participate in all three tenants, further alleviating the burden on the contributing sites and establishing scalability
- Experienced users of the N3C COVID Enclave were able to quickly establish proof of concept analytics results by importing reusable items from COVID projects, e.g. Concept sets for AKI diagnosis, analytical code for AKI detection from lab data, 'table 1' generation.
- Project teams were effective once they got going
- Positive learning environment for new N3C users

Challenges

- Hard to find documentation that described the tenant model
- Branding the Tenant model. (NCATS didn't approve N3C-Clinical, but it has already been used in congressional documents and other public locations)
- Overcoming reputational harm from communications that "N3C is ending", resulting in less interest in participating in the tenant.
- Governance
 - IRBs had a hard time conceptualizing the tenant model.
 - Perhaps creating intuitive infographics to support understanding by those not in the middle of this stuff every day
 - Sites' internal governance groups had a difficult conceptualizing the tenant model, specifically why all data had to be transferred rather than transferring data as needed for each project.
 - Confusion around the reliance process
 - DUA / DTA
 - Confusion between DUA/DTA with prior signatories
 - Combined DUA/DTA wasn't meant for non-data sites
- Hard to drive internal processes, when there isn't a tenant selected yet for the site
 - We had trouble identifying a site PI
- Responsibilities
 - Confusion about oversight responsibilities (Tenants/ N3C leadership/ NCATS) to adjudicate disputes within a Tenant
 - Confusion about role of Result Download Committee
- Data
 - Data start date can be somewhat limiting
 - Data quality requirements/ feedback loop with sites will be a long-term requirement for success
- Summer scheduling conflicted with the main pilot operational timeline. Operational delays.
- There was no funding allocated for personnel to work on the pilot projects beyond the establishment of the tenant itself. Roles of Clinician, Analyst, Project Manager were difficult to attract due to lack of compensation, and unclear outlook.

- Unfunded science can be challenging in terms of building strong teams
 - Enthusiasm for unfunded analytics in pilot phase unlikely to be sustained
 - Engaging local clinical experts to participate
 - Difficult to get enough SMEs to participate
- Monthly reports required by each site are burdensome
- Enclave onboarding is still taking significant time for new members. Consider improving instructions (centralizing on a single page).

Doing Things Differently

- Replace NIH security training with something specific to N3C and similar to AoUs
- Need longer-term guidance/ vision/funding for 3-5 years out.
- Supporting a tenant with researchers that are new to enclave heavier lift from a training perspective.
 - Will require new approaches.
- Short-term funding makes it difficult to grow and support teams. Can't hire or retain talent.
 - Also makes it difficult to maintain a team that can remain dedicated to the work
 - Too short timeline to make meaningful progress towards a paper
- Separate DTA from DUAs
 - Sites asked to separate the Data Use and Data Transfer requirements in the agreements. Sites who want to participate in the tenant project as a non-data submission site were required to sign the same agreements as those who were submitting data. This caused confusion at the sites and delayed agreement review and execution.
- Run a bootcamp on EHR data for tenant research teams at time of project launch.
 - Live session with opportunity for domain specific questions
- Needed value communication for new local infrastructure for tenant phenotype. If allowed, this could save effort at CTSA sites.
- SQL extraction script and exporter needs to be reviewed for data scale and optimization. Super slow.
- Need to data quality review & feedback for site data submitters
- Consider regional tenants that have tenants within tenants, e.g. will allow a set of regional organizations to collaborate on their shared data, but then provide access to subsets of these data for specific projects
- Other data types
 - How to engage with SMEs, what should their involvement be in governance?
 - enable easy registry/consented data ingest into the tenants
 - Support genomics workflows alongside EHR RWD analytics for new tenants

What Is Next?

- Communication
 - Aggressive communications about N3C Clinical, starting with branding.
 - Marketing of available resources to expand value across more communities.
 - Educational resources availability and working with the community to advance multidisciplinary workforce development.
 - Help desk support
- Convince NCATS to fund N3C Clinical and all the necessary components at a sustainable level.
 - Get all CTSAs/CTRs onboard
 - There is a cost for sites to submit data and to use data
 - Avoid perpetual volunteerism
- Gov regulatory
 - Plan for alignment of new multi-institutional grant proposals that want to use N3C structure.
 - R01 proposal planning is currently halted due to lack of clarity.
 - Talk EPIC/HHS into combining Cosmos +N3C
 - Clarify rewards and sanctions
 - Clarify instructions for participation & oversight
 - Update Governance docs (CoC, community guiding principles, etc. beyond COVID and the tenant pilot)
 - The main change to make in the future is to have a good setup to financially support the people who sign up to lead as well as funding for hiring support staff/analysts in a timely manner from time of project start.
- Limited Data Set as an option for research
- DTA/DUA changes requested by sites Adjust Attachment 1 to reflect no data will be transferred, which has been acceptable to the other sites.
 - Fund a Publication and Download Committee
 - Consider N3C Covid as another ~ Tenant
- Onboarding
 - "Guide to Tenant" → getting gov set up and analytics
 - "How to guide for new tenants"
 - How to scale training and support
- DUR Process
 - Community engagement - discussed potentially developing a community liaison similar to logic and data liaisons to engage with the community
 - Emotional and Data submission support money for sites
 - Agencies & Corporations as patrons for cost recovery

Term Usage count for concept sets

Suggest revision to agreements to support public visibility of aggregate tenant population features.

Purpose	To see anonymized frequencies of term usage across sites, allow for computation of overlap/similarity in concept sets, and other tools where empirical information about term usage may be useful.
Example	Modified versions of N3C Concept set browser, OHDSI Atlas
Scope	Visible to anyone who is registered with an account, including those without institutional DUAs.
Safeguards	Remove site IDs from any visualization. Show % of patients at a site with that code, not counts. Show grand total counts across all sites, i.e. row sums.
Purpose	To see aggregate data that showcases the size of the project, to provide simple views of patient counts to motivate feasibility.
Example	Current N3C COVID dashboards, phenotype explorer. https://covid.cd2h.org/
Scope	Visible to anyone on the web.
Safeguards	Pool all data from sites, never individual site information, allow state-wide counts after 20 sites have data available. Obscure cell sizes < 20.

Future of N3C

Infrastructure and community support

We attempted to quantify the amount of personnel effort spent on tenant pilot activities, but found it difficult in many cases to distinguish clearly between N3C COVID activity and 'tenant only' activity. Many of the activities currently funded by the N3C contract via Axle would necessarily become tenant-related activities if they were no longer being performed for N3C COVID. For example, office hours & helpdesk activities currently serve both projects, and would continue on behalf of tenants if COVID activity were to cease. Nonetheless, we provide the results of our estimates. These estimates suggest that approximately one third of total effort/cost from the N3C contract can be directly traced to tenant activities, i.e. those activities which would not be performed at all if the tenant pilot weren't around. We suggest, however, that any attempt to estimate a cost of running the tenant ecosystem should be considered under that assumption that N3C COVID activity and funding were to cease. The following is a condensed list of activities currently performed for the N3C COVID enclave that should be included in projected costs of managing a tenant enclave.

Conduct leadership, community governance, and compliance. Manage and maintain concept set creation and validation. Work within the Logic Liaison group to provide code templates and training to support sample projects. Work with data providing sites to facilitate two way data quality improvement and reporting. Monitor, maintain and improve data ingestion & harmonization. Provide education, community support, issue resolution, training, documentation, and best practices.

While one might hope that the volume of effort required to support a tenant based enclave is less than the current support for the N3C COVID enclave, many of these costs are somewhat inelastic with respect to the scale and number of sites and projects (leadership, tool developments, documentation), while other tasks are likely to scale up as the number of participating sites increases (DI&H), or the number of tenants increases (Education, community support, project management). Other less predictable costs should also be considered, such as the inclusion of new data sources, e.g. USRDS. Presumably the appetite to perform global data quality improvements (e.g. upgrading OMOP versions for sites, more detailed score cards, etc.) would also scale with the number of active tenants benefitting from any improvements.